

LINGUOCULTURAL BASES OF SOCIAL HOUSEHOLD EUPHEMISMS

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ABSTRACT

The article deals with the euphemic use of language units, which are one of the social features of the language, euphemic phenomena, the commonality of language and culture between them. It is noted that the study of the connection of language units with the context, the situation of speech only gives a full opportunity to correctly understand their meaning, which determines the need for sociolinguistic knowledge. It is noted that the cultural similarity of euphemisms stems from the uniformity of the tasks assigned to them. It is concluded that the use of euphemisms in speech often depends on the values that have developed in a particular society, the norms of etiquette and socio-cultural speech norms.

KEYWORDS: - Sociolinguistic studies, National mental factors, sociopragmatic studies, ethnolinguistics, ethnopsychology, cognitive psychology, psycholinguistics, sociolinguistics and social linguistics

In the current globalisation process, the integration of science and education, the relationship between various sciences as well as the boundary between them, acquires a rather relative character. Therefore, among all scientific directions in linguistics “...the task of comprehensive support of scientific and creative research, creation of the necessary conditions for them” indicates the need to conduct in-depth research on the integration of sciences. Attention to the state language in our country has increased to the level of the priority. Therefore, along with increasing the effectiveness of preserving, enriching and practically using our native language, special attention is paid to further increase the status of the state language and practically use linguistic opportunities of World linguistics whilst the application of language units in speech and revealing the features of meaning and function shows the necessity of this problem. The sociological aspect of the study of the language sector has long been of great interest to linguists. After all, language development, the changes in it are directly related to the development of society. In scientific sources, which existed until the beginning of the XX century, in the connection of linguistics with other sciences, the concepts related to sociolinguistics are described. The dictionary of linguistic terms states: “Sociolinguistics (lot. soci(etat) - society+linguistics) is a branch of linguistics studying the conditions

of social existence and social development. This field, consisting of the synthesis of sociology and Linguistics, deals with such problems as the connection of social life with language; active processes in the development of language under the influence of non-linguistic factors; the change in the ratio between the verbal and written form of language with the wide spread of radio, television, cinema etc., the tasks and forms of maintaining language. According to the analysis of scientific literature, sociolinguistics refers to the ability to present the national characteristics of autistic speech, including the social and cultural competence: knowledge of the customs, values, rituals and other national and cultural characteristics of the country, as well as the ability to compare the language with the country that is being studied. That is, to be able to choose discourse in a suitable communicative situation; to understand the essence of the problem that has arisen and the person providing the service of consent when necessary explaining to the customer; being able to choose language forms and applying or changing it in accordance with the professional text within the framework of communicative situations on the topic; being able to communicate in a natural, usual manner for them, which does not arouse admiration or bitterness to the native speakers. As noted above, the development of Sociolinguistics, which appeared at the intersection point of sociology and Linguistics studies, depends on the extent to which the fields are studied, of course. In scientific sources, the forms of sociolinguistic communication are classified as follows: in the process of education, in the family environment; in social groups; in residential, temporary community; in educational institutions, in the production community; in the broad masses of the people, in the public; in nationality, ethnic group; international, between ethnic groups; between citizens divided by age categories; in person; in everyday household life. One of the peculiarities of the language is the euphemist application of language units. Euphemist events reflect the commonality of language and culture in itself. They are inextricably linked with the emergence and growth of national-cultural characteristics of peoples. The issues of euphemism, its classification and its occurrence in speech have been extensively studied in Russian and European linguistics. In the XX-XXI centuries, a number of scientific studies on the problem of euphemistic lexical and its connection with other language phenomena arose. In particular, euphemism from a historical point of view was considered on the basis of ancient taboos and was analyzed on the basis of materials of Indo-European and Slavic-Baltic languages (L.A.Bulakhovsky, B.A.Larin, E.A.Reformatsky). In the last decades, scientists from Moscow, Petersburg, and Volgograd were engaged in the study of the means and goals of euphemism in the Russian language

(L.P.Krisin, V.P.Maskvin, V.Z.Sannikov, E.P.Senichkina). Among the works in this regard, L.A.Bulakhovsky, A.A.Reformatsky, B.A.Larin studied euphemisms from a historical point of view on the basis of ancient taboos. With the description of the means and goals of euphemism in the Russian language, L.P.Krisin, V.P.Maskvin, V.Z.Sannikov, and E.P.Senichki³ were engaged. A.M.Katsev, N.T.Boschaeva, N.L.Saakayan, Y.S.Baskova and E.O.Miloenko⁴ dissertations, A.In vildanova's thesis "Эвфемия и принцип вежливости в современном английском языке: гендерный аспект" comprehensively highlight the aspects of English gender euphemisms in English and Russian⁵. Whereas N.Baskakov revealed the problems of euphemistic nominations in the languages of the Altai people⁶. So, in Russian linguistics, the subject circle of euphemism is grouped as follows: 1) Expressing some physiological process and condition (expect a child-pregnant); 2) Representing certain parts of the human body; 3) Signifying a sexual relationship; 4) Signaling illness and death (French death – colloquial, feeling bad - sick); 5) Representing diplomatic concepts. L.P.Krisin correctly noted that in the communicative relations of diplomats and politicians there were euphemisms due to the need of use of cynical, directly naming words within the framework of the label. 6) representing some professional corn. It is used for the purpose of increasing the prestige of the profession. For example, a milkman is an operator of a milking machine, a sweeper is an operator of cleaning work. In Uzbek linguistics N.Ismatullaev and A.Omonturdiyev conducted the scientific work on a special study of the phenomenon of euphemism, their stylistic features, linguistic peculiarities of the euphemisms used in the speech of the breeder⁷. A.Omonturdiyev studied euphemisms in a wide range as an object of research in stylistics and studied the euphemistic of Uzbek speech in his monographs titled "Euphemisms of Uzbek speech", "Euphemisms of Professional speech", as well as other works such as "One word's dictionary", "The art of word application", "Brief euphemisms of Uzbek language". A.Mamatov, L.Raupova, Z.Kholmanova, X.Kadirova and D.Rustamova's scientific work of the influence of euphemist and dysphemistic units on the formation of phraseology, gender characteristics of euphemisms, author's euphemisms and metaphorical features of euphemisms used in the work "Boburnoma" were analyzed.

Used literature:

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